

Optimising the Risk-Return Trade-off of Property Portfolios: A Quantitative Approach Using Synthetic Modelling

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Abstract

This paper proposes a quantitative methodology for optimising the risk-return balance of a property portfolio. To this end, it employs fictitious but realistic data for a commercial property portfolio from various asset classes, and it examines the application of Markowitz's Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) to an existing property portfolio. The analysis results in a portfolio combination of the various assets below the efficiency curve, which is optimised using the Mean-Variance Model in combination with the Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS). This approach takes into account the limitations of applying the Mean-Variance Model to real estate portfolios. The optimisation of the composition of the properties can be demonstrated. The results show that a targeted reallocation of the portfolio to less correlated asset classes can significantly reduce volatility while maintaining the expected return. Concurrently, a higher Sharpe ratio can be evidenced through the implementation of the derived optimisation measures, illustrating an enhancement in the risk-adjusted return. The constant optimisation of the portfolio's risk-return balance is a central task in property portfolio management, and objective performance measurement remains crucial, despite the low liquidity and divisibility of properties. However, there is an absence of a uniform standard for the quantitative optimisation of property portfolios. This paper therefore examines the extent to which the principles of MPT can be combined with the possibilities of MCS for property portfolios.

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I. INTRODUCTION

THE optimisation of the risk-return profile and the associated measurement of risk have gained increasing importance in the real estate sector since the financial crisis of 2007-2008 [1]. Europe experienced the "worst recession since the founding of the EU" during this period. This can be attributed to the combination and the resulting impacts of the banking crisis and the increasing national debt in the Eurozone [2]. The development of property values was also affected. In the commercial real estate segment, property values fell from 106.5 points (annual average 2007) to 99.7 points (annual average 2009), as measured by the 'vdp property price index' [3].

After the financial crisis, the European Central Bank (ECB) continuously lowered interest rates. In 2014, the main refinancing rate was 0% for the first time. This is the rate at which banks can borrow money from the ECB [4]. This low-interest policy continued until 2022 and enabled many capital

providers to finance the purchased properties at favourable credit conditions. This led to increased demand, which resulted in a rise in property prices [5].

However, every boom phase is followed by a correction. Inflation, rising interest rates [5], exorbitant construction price increases in recent years [6], ESG regulations [7], and (geo-) political unrest are just some of the factors that negatively impacted the value development of property prices in Germany. There is a tense and crisis-ridden market environment [8]. The real estate industry is facing structural change, in which the importance of targeted optimisation between risk and return of property portfolios is increasing [9].

It is widely acknowledged that real estate constitutes a pivotal component within diversified investment portfolios, offering stable returns and inflation protection. However, in contrast to conventional financial assets such as equities and fixed-income securities, property investments are distinguished by illiquidity, heterogeneity, and market inefficiencies. Consequently, the optimisation of real estate portfolios poses significant challenges.

In recent years, portfolio theory – particularly the seminal work of Markowitz (1952) [10] on the risk-return trade-off – has been increasingly applied to real estate markets. However, the application is not straightforward due to limited data availability and the complexities involved in modelling real estate performance. Synthetic modelling has emerged as a promising tool to overcome these limitations, allowing for the simulation of asset behaviours and the construction of optimised portfolios in data-scarce environments.

The objective of the present paper is to develop a quantitative framework that employs synthetic modelling techniques to optimise the risk-return trade-off in property portfolios.

This study sets out to investigate whether Harry Markowitz's mean-variance model, when employed in conjunction with Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS), is a suitable methodology for deriving recommendations for action aimed at optimising risk-return ratios towards the creation of a minimum variance portfolio.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The optimisation of a portfolio's risk/return structure, and thus portfolio optimisation, has always been a key issue for investors in real estate portfolio management [10], [11] This applies to both institutional and private investors [12]. In their seminal work, Senescall and Low [11] provide a comprehensive

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overview of the historical research conducted on quantitative portfolio management strategies. These strategies encompass a range of approaches, including portfolio optimisation, risk parity, investment style integration, and machine learning. As demonstrated in the seminal work of Markowitz [13], there is a strong correlation between optimal portfolio composition and portfolio construction techniques.

In his seminal 1952 paper, Markowitz [14] set out his modern portfolio theory, which posits that investors can mitigate portfolio risk without compromising returns by strategically diversifying their investments. The pivotal element in this regard is not the selection of individual securities, but rather the manner in which they interact with one another within the broader portfolio, particularly the correlations between the investments. Markowitz demonstrated mathematically that for each level of risk, there exists an optimal portfolio that yields the highest expected return (i.e. the efficiency frontier). Investors are therefore advised to select portfolios that offer the optimal risk/return ratio for their individual risk profile. The concept of risk is measured through the range of returns, otherwise known as the variance or standard deviation. Diversification, on the other hand, serves to reduce what is termed 'unsystematic risk'.

Despite the evolution of portfolio management research, Markowitz's mean-variance model maintains its relevance and continues to be extensively cited [11]. The relative merits of these portfolio optimisation techniques in comparison to the simple 1/N portfolio remain a subject of debate [15], although these results are viewed critically by other researchers [16], [17].

A plethora of publications address the issue of portfolio optimisation in real estate markets. The study by Andrew, M., & Glenn, M. [18] analyses the inclusion of both public and private real estate in a mixed portfolio using the mean/variance Markowitz method of the efficient frontier without restrictions. The results, obtained from a 5-, 10-, 15- and 25-year study, demonstrate that both public and private real estate have the capacity to enhance efficiency frontiers to a significant degree. It is further suggested that these results may necessitate a higher allocation than is currently customary.

A recent study by Andrew, M., & Glenn, M. [18] analysed portfolio allocations over a 45-year period and examined the impact of direct real estate investments and public REITs in mixed investment portfolios. The study corroborates numerous extant research findings and also examines specific risk-return points along the Markowitz efficiency frontier.

In his article on the Chinese real estate market, Xu [19] presents an innovative approach to integrating quadratic programming (QP) into Markowitz portfolio optimisation. The objective of this study is to examine the efficacy and relevance of QP as a solution approach for portfolio issues, with the aim of reducing risk and increasing returns.

The most recent study by Konopasek [20] on the application of Markowitz theory to real estate portfolios in Austria analyses how individual assets can be optimally weighted in the overall portfolio in order to improve the risk/return ratio. According to the principles of Markowitz theory, it is recommended that a portfolio of assets be diversified in order to minimise unsystematic risk and increase the efficiency of the portfolio. The optimal portfolio mix is achieved through the combination

of assets with disparate risk and return profiles, whilst minimising correlation, thereby leveraging the diversification effect to its maximum potential.

In their seminal study, Lavell and Yamamoto [21] sought to examine the potential benefits of augmenting a diversified investment portfolio, comprising equities, bonds and real estate, with farmland holdings within the United States. To this end, the researchers employed the theoretical framework of modern portfolio theory, pioneered by Markowitz, to analyse the implications of such an investment strategy. Their findings, as highlighted by the authors, are of particular significance within the context of this particular investment category.

Monte Carlo simulation is predominantly employed within the domain of portfolio management for the optimisation of risk, or as a component of risk management methodologies [22] and a few for real estate valuation [23]. The significance of a well-developed risk management system in quantifying risks is illustrated by Gleißner and Wiegelmann [24], who employed Monte Carlo simulation to aggregate various risks in order to ascertain the overall risk for real estate developers.

A few of scientific papers and practical studies have been published which examine the optimisation of real estate portfolios using Markowitz theory in combination with Monte Carlo simulations.

In their study, Petropoulos et al. [25] sought to determine and maximise the economic added value of a real estate portfolio, taking into account risk in Greece. To this end, they employed the classic Markowitz model. The Monte Carlo simulation method is utilised to model the portfolio, with the debt-to-equity ratio being factored into the PERT distribution. The maximum weighting of residential real estate in the portfolio is determined to be 22.7%.

In the work of Fries [26], Monte Carlo simulation is utilised to evaluate a real estate portfolio comprising 20 properties. The study demonstrates that Monte Carlo simulation can realistically reflect uncertainties in input variables such as rents, vacancy rates and costs. This enables the risk distribution of the portfolio value to be quantified. The results of the study provide the portfolio manager with a probability distribution for the present value and other risk indicators.

To the author's knowledge, a uniform industry standard for the quantitative optimisation of the risk/return ratio specifically for a pure real estate portfolio has yet to be established. Existing standards primarily address the general optimisation of portfolios. Consequently, these publications are not suitable for comparative juxtaposition [27].

III. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

In this study an analysis will be conducted on a fictional real estate portfolio consisting of office, retail, and hotel properties. The synthetic modelling of a real estate portfolio under consideration comprises a total of twelve properties, located in the German cities of Hamburg, Munich and Frankfurt am Main. The current market value (as of 2024) of the portfolio is approximately €1.4 billion. The investor adopts a risk-averse approach and seeks to optimise the risk-return balance of the portfolio, with the objective of achieving a minimum variance portfolio.

A. Data base and model assumptions

In the research process, the creation of the fictional portfolio was carried out first. To simplify matters and due to time constraints, a static model was chosen. The program Excel was used for the calculation and analysis of all key figures as well as for conducting statistical tests.

Firstly, a fictitious portfolio consisting of 12 properties in three asset classes in the cities of Hamburg, Munich and Frankfurt am Main was created.

It is important to determine the location, acquisition year, usage type (office, retail, hotel, etc.), rental area, rental income, and Capital Expenditure (CapEx) costs for the properties. The selection of locations in the portfolio compilation was random; however, it was crucial that the selected locations and asset classes had peak yields. These were later used to derive the development of market values.

The rental area can be freely determined. To calculate rental income, it is advisable to derive it from the market rent of the year under consideration and to apply a premium or discount depending on the assumed condition of the property. Subsequently, the rental income can be back-calculated to the respective acquisition year. For this purpose, the back-calculation was carried out in 5% steps from the previous year's value. It is assumed that all properties have an occupancy rate of 100%. The costs for CapEx measures were calculated between 1.6% and 2.2%, measured against the respective rental income of the property, within the scope of this work.

The development of market values was based on the historical developments of location-specific prime yields. Thus, market values can be extrapolated from the time of acquisition. It is advisable to present the listed key figures and developments for each property in tabular form, as shown in Figure 1.

Object	Postcode	City	Type of use	Year of acquisition	Year of construction	Property size (m ²)	GLA (m ²)	Threat hotel (m ²)	Threat retail (m ²)	Threat office (m ²)	Threat residential (m ²)
1	20439	Hamburg	Office (100%)	2016	2013	1,300	6,530	-	-	6,530	-
2	22745	Hamburg	Hotel (100%)	2010	2003	15,640	33,626	33,626	-	-	-
[...]											
12	60408	Frankfurt (Main)	Office (50%), Retail (50%)	2012	2010	5,310	14,339	-	1,436	11,487	-

Object	Rental income in year 2010	[...]	Rental income in year 2024	Market value 2010	[...]	Market value 2024	Weighting on total Portfolio in %	CapEx 2010	[...]	CapEx 2024
1	-	-	1,175,000 €	-	-	33,550,000 €	2.4%	-	-	21,500 €
2	5,156,187 €	-	10,573,000 €	80,112,565 €	-	179,500,000 €	13.09%	113 €	-	211,460 €
[...]										
12	-	-	1,752,000 €	-	-	53,150,000 €	2.56%	-	-	35,040 €

Fig. 1: Tabular Portfolio Breakdown

B. Structure of the synthetic model and optimisation process

Additionally, the returns of the individual assets and the portfolio were calculated. In the further course, the term 'return' always refers to the object return, which is calculated by dividing the rental income of the respective year, minus the CapEx costs, by the market value of the object [30], unless otherwise specified. Figure 2 shows the individual returns from the respective acquisition year. These serve as the basis for the subsequent analyses.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11	Object 12	Risk-free interest rate
Object return 2010	6.29%	4.89%	4.89%	6.37%	4.89%	6.37%	4.89%	6.37%	4.89%	6.37%	4.89%	6.37%	2.80%
Object return 2011	6.10%	4.77%	4.90%	6.04%	4.77%	6.04%	4.77%	6.04%	4.77%	6.04%	4.77%	6.04%	1.83%
Object return 2012	5.78%	4.72%	4.75%	5.72%	4.72%	5.72%	4.72%	5.72%	4.72%	5.72%	4.72%	5.72%	1.80%
Object return 2013	5.79%	4.53%	4.60%	5.73%	4.53%	5.73%	4.53%	5.73%	4.53%	5.73%	4.53%	5.73%	0.80%
Object return 2014	5.49%	4.34%	4.36%	5.37%	4.34%	5.37%	4.34%	5.37%	4.34%	5.37%	4.34%	5.37%	0.60%
Object return 2015	5.26%	3.66%	3.90%	5.09%	3.66%	5.09%	3.66%	5.09%	3.66%	5.09%	3.66%	5.09%	0.21%
Object return 2016	3.14%	4.43%	3.47%	3.33%	4.55%	2.79%	3.15%	3.15%	3.15%	3.15%	3.15%	3.15%	0.19%
Object return 2017	2.97%	4.20%	3.09%	3.16%	3.84%	2.79%	2.90%	2.90%	2.90%	2.90%	2.90%	2.90%	-0.41%
Object return 2018	2.76%	2.94%	3.02%	3.84%	2.67%	2.68%	2.68%	2.68%	2.68%	2.68%	2.68%	2.68%	-0.21%
Object return 2019	2.44%	3.99%	2.79%	2.87%	4.41%	2.67%	2.54%	2.72%	2.67%	2.67%	2.67%	2.67%	-0.25%
Object return 2020	2.57%	4.57%	2.79%	2.99%	4.22%	2.57%	2.40%	2.72%	2.57%	2.57%	2.57%	2.57%	-0.25%
Object return 2021	2.57%	4.57%	2.79%	2.89%	4.22%	3.22%	2.93%	2.78%	2.71%	3.34%	4.13%	2.76%	-0.13%
Object return 2022	3.24%	5.28%	3.57%	3.86%	4.79%	4.13%	3.76%	3.57%	3.71%	3.86%	4.79%	3.83%	2.61%
Object return 2023	3.41%	5.78%	4.51%	4.92%	5.55%	5.13%	4.82%	4.59%	4.80%	4.47%	5.45%	5.09%	2.12%
Object return 2024	3.40%	5.77%	4.51%	4.91%	5.54%	5.12%	4.82%	4.60%	4.80%	4.46%	5.43%	4.89%	2.18%

Fig. 2: Development of Object Returns

A descriptive analysis of the existing portfolio was subsequently conducted. To represent the mean-variance model, the parameters shown in Figure 3 were first determined. The average return of the individual assets and the number (n) of object returns used are displayed. Additionally, the standard deviation is derived from the available object returns. The variance is calculated by squaring the standard deviation. Finally, the Sharpe Ratio was determined by the difference between the average return and the risk-free interest rate, followed by dividing by the standard deviation. Accordingly, Object 1 has the highest Sharpe Ratio with a value of 6.170. In contrast, Object 12 has the lowest ratio with a value of 2.580.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6
O - return	2.94%	5.17%	3.75%	3.96%	5.02%	4.40%
number of assets	9	15	14	15	15	4
Standard deviation	0.35%	0.74%	0.76%	0.81%	0.78%	0.79%
Variance	1.2457E-05	5.531E-05	5.7562E-05	6.6369E-05	6.1385E-05	6.2757E-05
O Risk-free interest rate	0.77%	1.08%	0.95%	1.08%	1.08%	1.68%
Sharpe-Ratio	6.170	5.494	3.686	3.530	5.025	3.438

	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11	Object 12
O - return	3.36%	3.66%	3.49%	4.03%	4.33%	4.07%
number of assets	11	14	11	4	8	4
Standard deviation	0.82%	0.91%	0.79%	0.47%	0.73%	0.93%
Variance	6.716E-05	8.2748E-05	6.1822E-05	2.2129E-05	5.3606E-05	8.5915E-05
O Risk-free interest rate	0.75%	0.95%	0.75%	1.68%	0.84%	1.68%
Sharpe-Ratio	3.186	2.981	3.484	5.015	4.770	2.580

Fig. 3: Key Information at the Asset Level

To calculate the portfolio return and the standard deviation at the portfolio level, the weighting of the individual objects in the portfolio was first calculated in Figure 4. The weighting was calculated based on the market values from 2024.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6
Weighting current portfolio	2.47%	13.09%	7.55%	4.58%	11.12%	14.23%
	13.86%	9.08%	14.59%	3.17%	3.69%	2.56%

Fig. 4: Weighting of the Current Portfolio by Rental Income

The portfolio return is 4.10% p.a. with a standard deviation of 0.73%. The variance-covariance matrix shown in Figure 5 is considered in the calculation of the portfolio standard deviation. The Sharpe Ratio of the current portfolio is measured at 4.120. This represents a positive return in relation to the risk-free interest rate.

Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11	Object 12	
Object 1	1.2457E-05	1.830E-05	2.144E-05	2.435E-05	1.571E-05	2.578E-05	2.533E-05	2.616E-05	2.536E-05	1.523E-05	2.281E-05	2.918E-05
Object 2	1.830E-05	3.331E-05	5.013E-05	5.822E-05	5.576E-05	3.890E-05	4.766E-05	6.008E-05	4.631E-05	2.306E-05	4.911E-05	4.490E-05
Object 3	2.144E-05	5.013E-05	3.756E-05	5.990E-05	5.192E-05	5.704E-05	5.030E-05	6.805E-05	3.388E-05	4.730E-05	6.658E-05	6.658E-05
Object 4	2.435E-05	5.822E-05	3.756E-05	6.637E-05	6.003E-05	6.660E-05	5.924E-05	7.160E-05	5.871E-05	3.954E-05	5.702E-05	7.760E-05
Object 5	1.571E-05	5.576E-05	5.192E-05	6.003E-05	6.138E-05	4.397E-05	4.410E-05	6.124E-05	4.418E-05	2.613E-05	4.303E-05	5.144E-05
Object 6	2.578E-05	3.890E-05	5.704E-05	6.660E-05	4.397E-05	6.286E-05	6.366E-05	6.870E-05	3.726E-05	4.308E-05	7.313E-05	7.313E-05
Object 7	2.533E-05	4.766E-05	5.030E-05	5.924E-05	4.410E-05	6.286E-05	6.248E-05	6.261E-05	3.734E-05	6.302E-05	7.549E-05	7.549E-05
Object 8	2.616E-05	6.008E-05	6.805E-05	7.160E-05	6.124E-05	6.366E-05	6.248E-05	6.060E-05	3.783E-05	5.897E-05	7.429E-05	7.429E-05
Object 9	2.536E-05	4.651E-05	5.109E-05	5.871E-05	4.418E-05	6.870E-05	6.261E-05	6.060E-05	6.182E-05	4.079E-05	5.882E-05	8.006E-05
Object 10	1.523E-05	2.306E-05	3.388E-05	3.954E-05	2.613E-05	3.726E-05	3.734E-05	3.783E-05	4.079E-05	2.213E-05	2.559E-05	4.347E-05
Object 11	2.281E-05	4.911E-05	4.730E-05	5.702E-05	4.303E-05	4.308E-05	6.302E-05	5.897E-05	5.882E-05	2.599E-05	3.261E-05	5.639E-05
Object 12	2.918E-05	4.490E-05	6.658E-05	7.760E-05	5.144E-05	7.313E-05	7.349E-05	7.429E-05	8.006E-05	4.347E-05	5.039E-05	8.391E-05

Fig. 5: Variance-Covariance Matrix of Current Portfolio

Furthermore, the efficient frontier is subsequently determined by a random matrix, which, upon renewal, outputs randomly generated portfolio configurations and thus constantly changing risk-return distributions. The matrix is shown in Figure 6. In order to enhance the efficiency of the revaluation of new portfolio configurations, the matrix is

expanded by 10,000 additional trials, which are carried out simultaneously.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	
Random matrix	0.360	0.580	0.748	0.772	0.368	0.751	
Arbitrary weighting	5.11%	8.24%	10.62%	10.95%	5.22%	10.66%	
	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11	Object 12	
Random matrix	0.547	0.801	0.382	0.371	0.758	0.608	7.045
Arbitrary weighting	7.76%	11.37%	5.42%	5.26%	10.76%	8.63%	100.00%
Portfolio return	4.03%						
Standard deviation	0.73%						
Sharpe-Ratio	4.045						

Fig. 6: Random Matrix

The 10,000 values are then plotted on a scatterplot as shown in Figure 7. To make the values more visible, the axis divisions were adjusted. As illustrated in the diagram, the coordinates required for delineating the efficiency frontier can be determined.

Fig. 7: Scatter Plot of the Efficient Frontier – Monte Carlo Simulation

The points at the outermost edge of the scatter plot were then transferred to the mean-variance model to clearly represent the efficient frontier. Figure 8 lists the variables of the efficient frontier depicted in the mean-variance model.

Standard deviation	Portfolio return
0.70%	4.47%
0.65%	4.38%
0.62%	4.23%
0.59%	3.95%
0.63%	3.67%

Fig. 8: Coordinates Efficient Frontier

Thereafter, the determined values can be transferred to a second diagram. Moreover, the diagram displays the assets, the current portfolio and the risk-free interest rate. This enables the determination of the area of the mean-variance model in which the portfolio is located, and the direction in which it needs to be optimised to achieve a portfolio with minimal variance.

Furthermore, a histogram derived from the MCS values provides an initial frequency distribution with regard to risk and return distribution. This enables the determination of whether both the current and the optimised portfolio are performing better or worse than the average of comparable portfolios.

Recommendations can be derived from the mean-variance model of the current portfolio. If the objective is to reduce the variance of the portfolio, it is advisable to sell off the assets with the highest standard deviation. Additionally, this strategy serves to generate liquidity. If a sale of existing assets from the portfolio under consideration is assumed, the next step involves recalculating the portfolio weighting and creating an updated variance-covariance matrix. Furthermore, the new portfolio

will be remodelled in the mean-variance model. This will indicate whether the effects of portfolio optimisation have become apparent.

The generated liquidity can be used for reinvestments, thereby improving the risk-return balance of the portfolio. For this purpose, the peak yields from the asset classes office, logistics, retail, hotel, healthcare properties, new-build multi-family houses, and existing multi-family houses are considered. A correlation matrix is first created from the provided peak yields. From this, it is derived which of the considered asset classes exhibit the lowest correlation. Objects from these asset classes can be examined for potential acquisition.

For the objects to be acquired, the same values are collected as before. Subsequently, the portfolio metrics under consideration are recalculated in the previously established tabular overview. For the calculation of the standard deviation at the portfolio level, a new variance-covariance matrix is created accordingly. The newly calculated portfolio return, standard deviation, and Sharpe ratio under the applied measures contribute to the comparability of the effectiveness in risk-return optimisation across different scenarios. Additionally, for the sake of comparability, a new correlation matrix is created, which includes the acquired assets. This allows for a comparison to see if the correlation has decreased on average compared to the original portfolio composition. Furthermore, the new portfolio composition is also modelled in the mean-variance model to make the diversification and portfolio optimisation effects visible.

IV. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS / SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Conducting the modelling

The histogram displaying the simulated standard deviations can be seen in Figure 9. From this, it is evident that the lowest standard deviation lies between 0.58% and 0.59%. Only two values fall within this spectrum. The highest standard deviation in the histogram lies between 0.79% and 0.80%, encompassing only one value. Out of all 10,000 generated values, a standard deviation of 0.71% is most frequently represented with 655 values. Thus, this data point can be considered the central point of the risk distribution and is highlighted in dark grey. Additionally, it can be inferred from the representation that only 15% of all values are equal to or below 0.73%, and thus are equal to or higher than the risk measure assessed in the current portfolio. The sample values are statistically significant with a correlation coefficient of 0.15 and a p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the thesis of the inefficiency of the current portfolio can be supported.

The frequency of this standard deviation can serve as an indication that the optimised portfolio has a standard deviation in the range of 0.70% to 0.71%. This would represent an improvement in the risk profile compared to the original portfolio and also reflect a frequently occurring risk measure.

For the return, the histogram of the Monte Carlo simulation consisting of the 10,000 values can be evaluated, as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 9: Histogram of Standard Deviation – MCS

Fig. 10: Histogram of Return – MCS

The histogram clearly shows that the return metrics range from 3.64% at the lowest value to 4.48% at the highest value. The lowest return is represented three times in the entire simulation, while the highest return occurs only once. The return is most frequently found in the range of 3.98% to 4.00%. In the area highlighted in green due to its significance, there are 706 values. This indicates that the current portfolio, with a return of 4.10%, already achieves a slightly higher return than the majority of all simulated portfolios.

To understand how strongly the individual assets in the portfolio correlate with each other, the correlation matrix for the current portfolio is shown in Figure 11. All correlation coefficients are colour-coded according to their correlation strength. A light grey colouring corresponds to a stronger correlation. The more the colouring transitions to a dark grey tone, the weaker the correlation becomes. The colouring was created using conditional formatting in Excel, so the highest values are marked in light grey and the lowest values in the correlation matrix are highlighted in dark grey. The computer-based application ensures objectivity in the colouring.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11	Object 12
Object 1	1	0.80324	0.90121	0.88215	0.73783	0.84239	0.82081	0.88842	0.88525	0.93775	0.84842	0.81178
Object 2	0.80324	1	0.89891	0.96994	0.95691	0.99236	0.91983	0.89833	0.89337	0.99117	0.95784	0.97940
Object 3	0.90121	0.89891	1	0.93353	0.95039	0.99771	0.93278	0.98106	0.98725	0.99997	0.99368	0.97442
Object 4	0.88215	0.96994	0.93353	1	0.94022	1.00000	0.96587	0.98097	0.97776	0.99987	0.94364	0.99578
Object 5	0.73783	0.95691	0.95039	0.94022	1	0.99896	0.88576	0.93500	0.92481	0.99951	0.91876	0.99663
Object 6	0.84239	0.99236	0.99771	1.00000	0.99896	1	0.99918	0.99304	1.00000	0.99990	0.99956	0.99993
Object 7	0.82081	0.91983	0.93278	0.96587	0.88576	0.99918	1	0.97594	0.97170	0.99965	0.94963	0.99835
Object 8	0.88842	0.89833	0.98106	0.98097	0.93500	0.99304	0.97594	1	0.98602	0.99774	0.92376	0.99044
Object 9	0.88525	0.89337	0.98725	0.97776	0.92481	1.00000	0.97170	0.98602	1	0.99990	0.93366	0.99954
Object 10	0.93775	0.99117	0.99997	0.99987	0.99951	0.99990	0.99965	0.99774	0.99990	1	0.99951	0.99702
Object 11	0.84842	0.95784	0.99368	0.94364	0.91876	0.99956	0.94963	0.92376	0.93366	0.99951	1	0.99863
Object 12	0.81178	0.97940	0.97442	0.99578	0.99663	0.99993	0.99835	0.99044	0.99954	0.99702	0.99863	1

Fig. 11: Correlation Matrix of the Target Portfolio

The displayed correlation coefficients range from a low of 0.73783 to a high of 0.99990. The average correlation coefficient of the portfolio is 0.95680. This value indicates a relatively high correlation between the individual assets, as this average correlation coefficient is close to 1. The colouring in the matrix also underscores this, as a significant majority of the values are highlighted in light grey, indicating a strong correlation between the values.

Object 1 stands out particularly, as it has the lowest correlation with all assets compared to the other objects in the portfolio. This is also evident from the light grey to dark grey colouring. The lowest correlation in the entire portfolio is between Object 1 and Object 5, with a correlation factor of 0.73783. The highest correlation exists between Object 9 and Object 10.

Overall, it is apparent that the high correlation between the individual assets means that the diversification effects in the portfolio are not optimally utilised. This can be attributed to the similar usage types of the objects and the high proportion of office properties in the portfolio. Even though these objects are located in different places, the overarching trend is still similar. This can significantly influence the portfolio's value development and should therefore be considered in the derivation of actions.

B. Representation of the efficient frontier

From the representation of the mean-variance model in Figure 12, it can be seen that the current portfolio does not lie on the efficient frontier and is considered inefficient according to modern portfolio theory. The capital market line intersects at the point where the standard deviation is 0.65% and the return is 4.38%. This risk-return ratio reflects the ideal portfolio. With a Sharpe Ratio of 5.077, this configuration would achieve the highest positive return in relation to the risk-free interest rate.

In contrast, the portfolio with the lowest variance, the minimum variance portfolio, which also comes with a lower expected return, lies at the point where the standard deviation is 0.59% and a portfolio return of 3.95% is forecasted. The Sharpe Ratio is 4.864.

Fig. 12: Mean-Variance Model of the Current Portfolio

In the further course, it will be determined whether restructuring the portfolio towards the identified minimum variance portfolio based on derived actions is sensible from a quantitative perspective.

C. Comparison of different portfolio strategies

1) Excel Solver as an Instrument for Portfolio Optimisation

To optimise the current portfolio and bring it onto the efficient frontier, it is first crucial to determine the optimal portfolio weighting. The representation of the efficient frontier in the mean-variance model shows that the optimal minimum variance portfolio has a standard deviation of 0.59% and a portfolio return of 3.95%. This can be captured using the Solver function in Excel. The calculation revealed that no solution for the optimal portfolio with a standard deviation of 0.59% and a portfolio return of 3.95% can be found under the condition that all capital is invested. For this reason, another condition was added, limiting the portfolio return to be $\geq 3.95\%$ to approximate the given value of the efficient frontier. Figure 13 shows the optimal weighting for constructing a minimum variance portfolio.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6
Weighting	4.33%	14.84%	6.88%	7.66%	13.09%	9.69%

	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11	Object 12	Total weighting
Weighting	3.13%	6.49%	6.44%	8.00%	9.40%	10.05%	100.00%

Portfolio return	4.24%
Standard deviation	0.71%
Sharpe-Ratio	4.472

Fig. 13: Weighting of the Minimum Variance Portfolio Using Excel Solver

The representation shows that the Solver function has reallocated the capital distribution among the individual assets. However, it should be noted that this model is particularly impractical for optimising a real estate portfolio, as real estate is not as liquid. If it were a stock portfolio, such an optimisation method would be optimal, as it is time-efficient and a sale or asset reallocation can be quickly executed, reflecting a more liquid market than real estate.

2) Deriving Recommendation 1

As this work aims to optimise the existing portfolio towards a minimum variance portfolio, it is advisable to sell off the assets with the highest standard deviation. Both assets are orbited in Figure 14. The two assets to be sold are Object 8 and Object 12. Both objects have a relatively low return in relation to their associated risk profile.

Fig. 14: Assets to be Removed (orbited) from the Current Portfolio

The updated metrics for the target portfolio are shown in Figure 15. The new portfolio weighting can also be found in Figure 15.

TABLE X

OVERVIEW OF METRICS AND WEIGHTINGS OF THE TARGET PORTFOLIO

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10
Return	2.94%	5.17%	3.75%	3.96%	5.02%	4.40%	3.36%	3.49%	4.03%	4.33%
Number of assets	9	15	14	15	15	4	11	11	4	8
Standard deviation	0.35%	0.74%	0.76%	0.81%	0.78%	0.79%	0.82%	0.79%	0.47%	0.73%
Variance	1.2457E-05	5.5309E-05	5.7562E-05	6.6369E-05	6.1384E-05	6.2757E-05	6.7160E-05	6.1822E-05	2.2120E-05	5.3605E-05
Sharpe-Ratio	5.280	5.495	5.517	5.511	5.026	4.189	2.787	3.069	6.280	4.435

Target portfolio	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10
Weighting	2.79%	14.82%	8.55%	5.19%	12.59%	16.10%	15.69%	16.51%	3.58%	4.17%

Portfolio return	4.14%
Standard deviation	0.71%
Sharpe-Ratio	4.285

Fig. 15: Assets to be Removed (orbited) from the Current Portfolio

The updated variance-covariance matrix is illustrated in Figure 16.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	Object 7	Object 8	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11
Object 1	1.257E-05	1.8391E-05	2.1444E-05	2.4144E-05	1.9707E-05	2.3784E-05	2.5302E-05	2.5802E-05	1.5232E-05	2.2899E-05	
Object 2	1.8391E-05	1.3359E-05	5.0120E-05	4.8231E-05	5.1973E-05	3.8909E-05	4.7664E-05	4.6513E-05	3.3660E-05	4.9114E-05	
Object 3	2.1444E-05	5.0120E-05	7.5625E-05	5.9900E-05	5.1922E-05	5.7035E-05	5.0965E-05	5.1898E-05	3.3871E-05	4.7297E-05	
Object 4	2.4144E-05	4.8231E-05	5.9900E-05	6.6188E-05	6.0048E-05	6.6599E-05	5.9292E-05	5.8713E-05	3.9543E-05	5.7023E-05	
Object 5	1.9707E-05	5.1973E-05	5.1922E-05	6.0048E-05	6.1384E-05	4.3974E-05	4.4803E-05	4.418E-05	2.6169E-05	4.3084E-05	
Object 6	2.3784E-05	3.8909E-05	5.7035E-05	6.6599E-05	4.3974E-05	6.2757E-05	6.2856E-05	6.8793E-05	3.7262E-05	4.3076E-05	
Object 7	2.5302E-05	4.7664E-05	5.0292E-05	5.9292E-05	4.4103E-05	6.2856E-05	6.7160E-05	6.2612E-05	3.7342E-05	6.3017E-05	
Object 8	2.5802E-05	4.6513E-05	5.1898E-05	5.8713E-05	4.418E-05	6.8793E-05	6.2612E-05	6.0703E-05	5.9280E-05	5.9280E-05	
Object 9	1.5232E-05	3.3660E-05	3.3871E-05	3.9543E-05	2.6126E-05	3.7262E-05	3.7342E-05	4.9792E-05	2.2120E-05	2.5958E-05	
Object 10	2.2899E-05	4.9114E-05	4.7297E-05	5.7023E-05	4.3084E-05	4.3076E-05	6.3017E-05	5.9280E-05	3.8657E-05	3.8657E-05	

Fig. 16: Variance-covariance matrix under recommendation 1

The tabular representation shows that the standard deviation of the target portfolio is 0.71%. Thus, the standard deviation was reduced by -0.02 percentage points compared to the current state of the portfolio. The portfolio return of the target portfolio is 4.14%, achieving an increase of +0.04 percentage points. It is evident that the return increased slightly due to the sale of Objects 8 and 12. At the same time, the risk measure was reduced, which is in the investor's interest. Although the reduction in the risk measure seems very small, it should be noted that a diversified real estate portfolio experiences fewer fluctuations in return ratios compared to, for example, stock markets. As previously explained, this is related to the illiquid assets reflected in the real estate sector. This is also evident in the narrow curve depicted by the efficient frontier in the mean-variance model. The mean-variance model, in which the target portfolio is depicted, can be seen in Figure 17. This also shows the slight change in the portfolio value indicated by the dark grey dot towards the efficiency curve.

Fig. 17: Mean-Variance Model of the Target Portfolio under recommendation 1

Furthermore, the standard deviation value of the target portfolio can be further validated by the results of the Excel Solver function illustrated in Figure 13. Although this computer-based model is unsuitable for calculating the optimal capital distribution in a real estate portfolio, it still shows the same standard deviation that can be optimally achieved in the

portfolio under review with a return of 4.24%. Nevertheless, the model has limitations and cannot perform independent calculations to capture various portfolio configurations from other asset classes and integrate them into the calculation of the optimal portfolio weighting.

Supporting the results of the Excel Solver are the values generated from the MSC, which are presented in the form of histograms in Figures 9 and 10. By combining both histograms, it is shown that the most likely risk measure of such a real estate portfolio is 0.71%, with the most frequently occurring return between 3.98% and 4.00%. This illustrates that the optimised portfolio, with a standard deviation of 0.71% and a return of 4.14%, lies in a statistically stable range and slightly above the expected average. Thus, the results of the MCS support the usefulness of the proposed optimisation measure.

Additionally, the Sharpe Ratio of the current portfolio can be compared with that of the target portfolio. The Sharpe Ratio of the target portfolio is 4.285, while that of the current portfolio is 4.120. Even in the direct comparison of this metric, it is clear that the target portfolio generates a higher excess return compared to the risk-free investment than the current portfolio.

From the direct comparison of the metrics, it can be inferred that the measure of selling two objects with high volatility and relatively low return contributes to reducing risk while simultaneously achieving an increase in return.

3) Deriving Recommendation 2

Through the derivation of Recommendation 1, a slight effect on optimising the risk-return balance of the target portfolio compared to the current portfolio was evident. Further potential could be exhausted by utilising liquid capital amounting to € 159,650,000 from the sale of Objects 8 and 12 to invest in assets with different usage types, thereby enhancing the diversification effects in the portfolio. To do this, it is necessary to consider the correlations between the individual asset classes. To make this consideration, it is first important to capture the current prime yield developments of the individual asset classes. All subsequent calculations for Recommendation 2 are based on the population of the prime yields.

When evaluating the return developments, it is particularly noticeable that logistics properties have the highest standard deviation at 1.26%, closely followed by healthcare properties with a standard deviation of 1.17%. In contrast, new-build multi-family houses have very low standard deviations, at only 0.35%. Thus, this asset class can also be referred to as a 'safe haven'.

The corresponding correlation matrix, based on the developments of prime yields, is depicted in Figure 18.

The matrix shows that the correlation coefficients range from 0.82778 to 0.98438. Healthcare and logistics properties have the highest correlations with each other. In contrast, logistics and new-build multi-family houses generally show the lowest correlations. The asset class of logistics properties achieves an average correlation coefficient of 0.89567. For new-build multi-family houses, this is 0.89411.

	Office	Logistics	Retail (High Street)	Hotel	Healthcare (Nursing homes)	Multi-family homes (Existing properties)	Multi-family homes (New build)
Office	1.00000	0.86750	0.97061	0.94196	0.90251	0.95764	0.82778
Logistics	0.86750	1.00000	0.80895	0.88966	0.98438	0.88361	0.83559
Retail (High Street)	0.97061	0.80895	1.00000	0.97048	0.87003	0.93056	0.87839
Hotel	0.94196	0.88966	0.97048	1.00000	0.93617	0.93134	0.92055
Healthcare (Nursing homes)	0.90251	0.98438	0.87003	0.93617	1.00000	0.92798	0.90664
Multi-family homes (Existing properties)	0.95764	0.88361	0.93056	0.93134	0.92798	1.00000	0.89583
Multi-family homes (New build)	0.82778	0.83559	0.87839	0.92055	0.90064	0.89583	1.00000
Average correlation coefficient	0.92400	0.89567	0.91843	0.94145	0.93167	0.93242	0.89411

Fig. 18: Correlation Matrix of Various Usage Types (Germany)

The lowest correlation can be demonstrated between new-build multi-family houses and office properties. From this, it can be inferred that to optimise the risk-return balance of the current portfolio, logistics properties and new-build multi-family houses should be examined during the acquisition processes. If the examined objects meet the acquisition criteria, the purchase of such assets can positively impact the diversification effects of the portfolio. This must also be quantitatively demonstrated.

The investor was able to identify two logistics and two new-build residential properties that could be considered for acquisition. The locations of the two logistics properties are in Hamburg and Frankfurt (Main). The residential properties are located in Berlin and Hamburg.

In an acquisition scenario, Object 13 can have an annual net cold rent of € 3,429,602.89 and a market value of € 47.5 million. For the implementation of CapEx measures, a flat rate of 2% of the annual net cold rent was calculated for all acquisition objects. This results in an object return of 7.08%.

Object 14 has rental income of € 1,472,658.36 with a market value of € 27.2 million. The object return is 5.31%.

In the residential segment, Object 15 can have an annual net cold rent of € 1,962,962.96. The market value is € 53.0 million, and the object return is 3.63%.

For Object 16, which is located in Hamburg, annual rental income of € 1,221,198.16 can be demonstrated with a market value of € 26.5 million. The object return is 4.52%.

Figure 19 lists the key metrics regarding the subsequent portfolio analysis.

	Object 13	Object 14	Object 15	Object 16
Return	6.93%	5.95%	3.50%	3.90%
Number of assets	14	14	12	12
Standard deviation	1.37%	1.44%	0.33%	0.39%
Variance	0.00018754	0.000207736	1.08555E-05	1.53804E-05
Sharpe-Ratio	4.272	3.379	7.331	7.178

Fig. 19: Overview of Metrics for Acquisition Objects

The Figure shows that the two logistics properties have high volatility in return development. As a result, the risk measure, expressed by the standard deviation, is relatively high at 1.37% and 1.44%.

However, both objects can achieve high returns compared to the other objects in the portfolio. The opposite phenomenon occurs with Objects 15 and 16. These have a low standard deviation of 0.33% and 0.39%, respectively. Additionally, both objects have the highest Sharpe Ratio of all assets in the portfolio, with values of 7.331 and 7.178. Figure 20 provides an overview of the metrics. The new portfolio weighting resulting

from the acquisition of the four objects was also determined. The calculation was again based on the market values of 2024.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	Object 7
Weighting	2.48%	13.15%	7.58%	4.60%	11.17%	14.28%	13.92%
O - return	2.94%	5.17%	3.75%	3.96%	5.02%	4.40%	3.36%
Number of assets	9	15	14	15	15	4	11
Standard deviation	0.35%	0.74%	0.76%	0.81%	0.78%	0.79%	0.82%
Variance	1.2457E-05	5.53099E-05	5.75625E-05	6.6369E-05	6.13849E-05	6.27572E-05	6.71601E-05
Sharpe-Ratio	5.278	5.494	3.516	3.530	5.025	4.188	2.787
	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11	Object 13	Object 14	Object 15	Object 16
Weighting	14.65%	3.18%	3.70%	3.48%	1.99%	3.88%	1.94%
O - Rendite	3.49%	4.03%	4.33%	6.93%	5.95%	3.50%	3.90%
n	11	4	8	14	14	12	12
Standardabweichung	0.79%	0.47%	0.73%	1.37%	1.44%	0.33%	0.39%
Varianz	6.18222E-05	2.21291E-05	5.36057E-05	0.00018754	0.000207736	1.08555E-05	1.53804E-05
Sharpe-Ratio	3.068	6.278	4.434	4.272	3.379	7.331	7.178

Portfolio return	4.25%
Standard deviation	0.70%
Sharpe-Ratio	4.529

Fig. 20: Overview of Metrics for the Target Portfolio Under Recommendation

The acquisition of all four objects would positively impact the risk-return profile of the portfolio through the resulting diversification effects. Considering the second recommendation, the target portfolio's return is 4.25%, compared to the original portfolio's return of 4.10%. This value is accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.70%, compared to 0.73% in the current state. The Sharpe Ratio was optimised from a value of 4.120 for the current portfolio to a Sharpe Ratio of 4.529.

An updated variance-covariance matrix was created for the calculation of the standard deviation at the portfolio level.

From a statistical perspective, the standard deviation of 0.70% lies precisely in the significant range of values simulated by the MCS. The significant range of portfolio return expectation in the simulation was between 3.98% and 4.00%. The target portfolio under Recommendation 2 achieves a portfolio return of 4.24%, surpassing many comparable portfolios.

The diversification effects can be further illustrated and demonstrated in the correlation matrix shown in Figure 21 and the mean-variance model shown in Figure 22.

	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4	Object 5	Object 6	Object 7	Object 9	Object 10	Object 11	Object 13	Object 14	Object 15	Object 16
Object 1	1.00000	0.80322	0.92121	0.88215	0.73783	0.94259	0.82081	0.88325	0.93775	0.84842	0.91445	0.69342	0.90521	0.66667
Object 2	0.80322	1.00000	0.93891	0.96094	0.95691	0.99296	0.91983	0.93557	0.99117	0.99584	0.78999	0.68792	0.56110	0.68551
Object 3	0.92121	0.93891	1.00000	0.98393	0.95039	0.99977	0.93278	0.98755	0.99997	0.92428	0.90478	0.80055	0.72002	0.82947
Object 4	0.88215	0.96094	0.98393	1.00000	0.94028	1.00000	0.96587	0.99776	0.99987	0.94364	0.83079	0.70368	0.61799	0.80451
Object 5	0.73783	0.95691	0.95039	0.94028	1.00000	0.99896	0.88576	0.92481	0.99951	0.91876	0.84320	0.76812	0.70173	0.78202
Object 6	0.94259	0.99296	0.99977	1.00000	0.99896	1.00000	0.99918	1.00000	0.99990	0.99896	0.98617	0.99098	0.71748	0.77381
Object 7	0.82081	0.91983	0.93278	0.96587	0.88576	0.99918	1.00000	0.97170	0.99965	0.94963	0.61470	0.34982	0.38818	0.71833
Object 9	0.88325	0.93557	0.98755	0.99776	0.92481	1.00000	0.97170	1.00000	0.99990	0.93866	0.76732	0.54153	0.55218	0.78121
Object 10	0.93775	0.99117	0.99997	0.99987	0.99951	0.99990	0.99965	0.99990	1.00000	0.99951	0.98371	0.99034	0.72724	0.78266
Object 11	0.84842	0.99584	0.92428	0.94364	0.91876	0.99896	0.94963	0.93557	0.99951	1.00000	0.67045	0.39999	0.54445	0.68892
Object 13	0.91445	0.78999	0.90478	0.83079	0.84320	0.98617	0.61470	0.76732	0.98371	0.67045	1.00000	0.96558	0.86666	0.70954
Object 14	0.69342	0.68792	0.80055	0.70368	0.76812	0.99098	0.34982	0.54153	0.99034	0.39199	0.96558	1.00000	0.89297	0.62417
Object 15	0.50521	0.56110	0.72002	0.61799	0.70173	0.71748	0.81811	0.55218	0.72724	0.54445	0.86666	0.89297	1.00000	0.81485
Object 16	0.66667	0.68551	0.82947	0.80451	0.78202	0.77381	0.71833	0.77812	0.78266	0.66892	0.70954	0.62417	0.81485	1.00000

Fig. 21: Correlation Matrix of the Target Portfolio Considering Recommendation 2

The correlation matrix shows that the acquisition objects have low correlation coefficients. Object 15 has the lowest correlations with the other objects. The lowest correlation is between Objects 14 and 7, with a correlation coefficient of 0.34982. The average correlation coefficient was reduced from 0.96040 for the current portfolio to 0.84899, indicating that the average strength of the linear relationship between the variables has decreased.

Since some assets in the portfolio are more strongly correlated than others, this illustrates that the diversification effects in the portfolio are increasing, resulting in a lower risk measure at the portfolio level. This effect can also be seen in the mean-variance model in Figure 22.

Fig. 22: Mean-Variance Model Considering Recommendation 2

It shows that the dark grey point representing the portfolio return moves closer to the efficient frontier curve. The portfolio return has increased, while the standard deviation and thus the risk taken have decreased.

At the same time, it becomes clear that the derived recommendations have contributed to optimising the risk-return balance. However, it should be noted that it is not possible to invest the released capital arbitrarily in individual acquisition objects. The mean-variance model of the optimised portfolio shows that while the risk-return balance can be optimised towards the efficient frontier and approached, the optimised real estate portfolio cannot be brought to the efficiency point or the point of the optimal minimum variance portfolio.

V. DISCUSSION

To create a quantitative approach for optimising the risk-return balance of a real estate portfolio, quantitative analysis methods were applied in this work to analyse the current state of a portfolio. The application of standardised statistical methods ensures that the results are reproducible. The MPT by Harry Markowitz significantly formed the theoretical foundation of the investigation. The analysis approach highlights that the current portfolio composition lies below the efficiency curve. Using the MCS the efficient frontier and key points of the risk-return distribution were determined from a statistical perspective. By illustrating the assets in the mean-variance model, a suboptimal weighting of these was identified, and inefficiencies became visible. As a result, potential from restructuring the portfolio can be utilised to optimise the risk-return balance of the portfolio. Consequently, two concrete recommendations were derived to contribute to achieving this goal.

The theoretical expectations that the target portfolio should be optimised towards the point of the minimum variance portfolio of the efficient frontier were only partially fulfilled.

To objectively derive and evaluate actions to achieve this goal, the Excel Solver function was considered as an instrument for portfolio optimisation. However, this computer-based model reached its limits and proved not optimal for real estate portfolio optimisation. While this function can determine optimal portfolio weightings under predefined conditions, its suitability lies more in its application to a securities portfolio. This can be justified by the fact that the real estate market is less

liquid, and portfolio reallocation cannot be carried out arbitrarily.

For this reason, an alternative approach was pursued. Using the mean-variance model, two assets were identified that had a high standard deviation in relation to their returns. The sale of these assets already led to an optimisation of the risk-return balance of the portfolio under consideration.

In further steps, the creation and application of correlation matrices enabled the correlations between the individual assets in the portfolio and the asset classes considered in the top-7 locations to be shown. It was demonstrated that diversification effects can be achieved through assets with low correlations and their suitable combination. Particularly low-correlating assets lead to a reduction in portfolio volatility. Although modern portfolio theory is generally applied in the context of securities portfolio optimisation, this theoretical concept could also be applied to a real estate portfolio, especially in terms of illustrating diversification effects.

The values generated by the MCS, shown in the corresponding histograms, identified the statistical probabilities of certain return and standard deviation levels occurring. Additionally, the model showed that there are many portfolio configurations at the identified levels to achieve a specific risk-return ratio. The simulation also contributed to creating the efficient frontier. However, it should be noted that these are always random variables, and slightly different values are determined in each simulation. In this context, it may be advisable to generate the efficient frontier through programming to obtain an even more reliable and precise result.

Furthermore, the Sharpe Ratio was used to evaluate the risk-adjusted return. In the direct comparison between the current and target portfolios, the optimised portfolio showed a higher Sharpe Ratio, underscoring the effectiveness of the proposed optimisation measures. By conducting this analysis approach, the effectiveness of the actions in their possible implementation could also be evaluated.

According to the theory developed by Markowitz, the implementation of the proposed actions minimises unsystematic risk.

A significant contribution of this work lies in investigating a quantitative framework that enables the objective evaluation of the risk-return balance of a real estate portfolio to derive recommendations for portfolio optimisation and assess their efficiency. While many previous studies focus on conventional financial instruments, this work demonstrated that the combination of the mean-variance model and the Monte Carlo simulation also offers optimisation approaches that can be applied in real estate portfolio optimisation. A quantitative approach was successfully investigated, allowing the objective evaluation of the risk-return profile of real estate portfolios and deriving and assessing the efficiency of corresponding recommendations. However, it was also found that it was not possible to optimise the portfolio's risk-return profile to the point of the minimum variance portfolio of the efficient frontier, as asset reallocation in real estate investments cannot be carried out arbitrarily.

Further limitations of the work can be seen in the analysis of only a fictional portfolio. The assumed values are based on (partly generalised) assumptions. Additionally, the analysis assumed that there is no vacancy in the objects, which is rarely

the case in reality. The development of market values was oriented towards real market value developments. Moreover, it is a static model in which all costs and value developments are presented. Transferring and conducting a similar analysis in a dynamic model would require higher analytical effort. However, optimisation measures coordinated with asset management can be captured more precisely and their impact on the portfolio's risk-return balance can be reflected.

The findings show that MPT has limitations in real estate portfolio optimisation and should be complemented by a more holistic approach. Due to constraints in asset allocation, exact positioning on the efficient frontier is rarely achievable, though portfolio trends can be influenced. Still, using the mean-variance model—especially in combination with Monte Carlo simulation—proved valuable. Metrics like return and standard deviation effectively quantify performance and risk.

VI. CONCLUSION & OUTLOOK

This study addressed the central question: "Is Harry Markowitz's mean-variance model, combined with Monte Carlo simulation, suitable for optimizing the risk-return balance of a real estate portfolio?" The findings indicate that this can be affirmed with certain limitations. The combined approach allows for a quantitative analysis of portfolio performance using key metrics such as return, risk, variance, and asset correlation. However, challenges arise due to the low liquidity of real estate, which limits flexible asset reallocation and requires methodological adjustments. The optimisation process revealed inefficiencies that could be reduced, particularly by selling highly volatile assets and reallocating towards logistics and new-build residential properties. This improved diversification, reduced volatility, and increased the Sharpe Ratio. Nonetheless, the model assumes continuous tradability and market data availability—conditions not fully met in real estate. Future studies should incorporate liquidity risks and sector-specific dynamics more closely. While statistical methods like MPT and Monte Carlo simulation offer valuable optimisation tools for real estate portfolios, further adjustments are needed to fully reflect the unique characteristics of the real estate market. The results show that further research is needed, particularly to address real estate-specific factors like illiquidity and limited data transparency. The static model used limits responsiveness to market changes, and generalised assumptions may not reflect reality. Future work should apply a dynamic model and consider hybrid approaches that integrate qualitative factors, such as market sentiment. This study provides a basis for ongoing optimisation of real estate portfolios.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Dohmen, "Die Finanzkrise von 2007/2008 und ihre Folgen," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bpb.de/themen/wirtschaft/finanzwirtschaft/524122/die-finanzkrise-von-2007-2008-und-ihre-folgen/>. [Accessed 19 01 2025].
- [2] K.-H. Lehne, "Analyse Nr. 5 - Welche Lehren hat die EU aus der Finanz- und Staatsschuldenkrise 2008-2012 gezogen?," Europäischer Rechnungshof, Luxemburg, 2020.
- [3] A. Kunert, "vdp-Immobilienpreisindex," 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.pfandbrief.de/site/de/vdp/immobilie/finanzierung_und_markt/vdp-immobilienpreisindex.html#. [Accessed 06 01 2025].

- [4] U. Prof. Dr. Neyer, "Niedrigzinsen – die Rolle der Geldpolitik," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.wirtschaftsdienst.eu/inhalt/jahr/2020/heft/1/beitrag/niedrig-zinsen-die-rolle-der-geldpolitik.html>. [Accessed 19 01 2025].
- [5] E. Stampfl, "EZB-Leitzins: Verlauf, Statistik und Prognose," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.infina.at/trends/ezb-leitzins/>. [Accessed 19 01 2024].
- [6] C. Schmidt, "Baupreise geben nur leicht nach," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bbsr.bund.de/BBSR/DE/forschung/fachbeitraege/bauen/bauwirtschaft/baupreisprognose/baupreisprognose.html>. [Accessed 19 01 2025].
- [7] S. Zollinger and R. Simone, "Emerging Trends in Real Estate®: Europe 2024," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pwc.ch/en/insights/real-estate/europe-2024.html>. [Accessed 19 01 2025].
- [8] B. Leschkowski, "Politische Entscheidungen und globale wirtschaftliche Trends – Welche Auswirkungen haben sie auf den Immobilienmarkt?," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://verumvest.com/politische-entscheidungen-und-globale-wirtschaftliche-trends-welche-auswirkungen-haben-sie-auf-den-immobilienmarkt/>. [Accessed 19 01 2025].
- [9] K. Prof. Dr. Hennig and H. V. Dr. Volckens, "WHITE PAPER #2 IMMOBILIENWIRTSCHAFT UND DEMOGRAPHISCHER WANDEL – AUSWIRKUNGEN, POTENTIALE, RISIKEN Eine Betrachtung der Assetklassen Office, Living und Retail," EBS Real Estate Management Institute, Wiesbaden, 2023.
- [10] S. Hudson-Wilson, *Modern Real Estate Portfolio Management*, Frank J. Fabozzi Associates, 2020.
- [11] M. Senescall und R. K. Y. Low, *Quantitative Portfolio Management: Review and Outlook*. Mathematics, Bd. 12, 2024, pp. 1-25. Article 2897.
- [12] N. Torre und A. Rudd, "The Portfolio Management Problem of Individual Investors: A Quantitative Perspective," *The Journal of Wealth Management*, pp. 56-63, 2004.
- [13] L. Youssef, *Quantitative Analysis of Financial Markets: Essays on Multi-Asset Portfolio Management Topics*, E. B. School, Hrsg., 2024.
- [14] H. Markowitz, "Portfolio Selection," *J. Finance*, Bd. 7, p. 77–91, 1952.
- [15] V. DeMiguel, L. Garlappi und U. Raman, "Optimal Versus Naive Diversification: How Inefficient is the 1/N Portfolio Strategy?," *The Review of Financial Studies*, Bd. 22, Nr. 5, p. 1915–1953, 2007.
- [16] C. Kirby und B. Ostdiek, "It's All in the Timing: Simple Active Portfolio Strategies that Outperform Naïve Diversification," *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, Bd. 47, p. 437–467, 2012.
- [17] J. Tu und G. Zhou, "Markowitz meets Talmud: A combination of sophisticated and naive diversification strategies," *Journal of Financial Economics*, Bd. 99, Nr. 1, 2011.
- [18] M. Andrew and M. Glenn, "Public and Private Real Estate in a Mixed-Asset Portfolio," *Journal of Real Estate Portfolio Management*, vol. 9, no. 3, p. 193–203, 2003.
- [19] G. R. Mueller and A. G. Mueller, "Investable Real Estate Allocations in a Mixed Asset Portfolio; Both Long Term and During Different Cycles," *Journal of Real Estate Portfolio Management*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 91-102, 2023.
- [20] A. Konopasek, "APPLYING MARKOWITZ'S PORTFOLIO THEORY: REAL ESTATE INVESTMENTS WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF IDEAL ASSET ALLOCATION," *Master Thesis*, 2024.
- [21] B. Lavelle und K. Yamamoto, "Revisiting the Portfolio Diversification Impact of Farmland," *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, Bd. 26, Nr. 3, pp. 110-119, 2024.
- [22] C.-O. Amédée-Manesme, M. Baroni, F. Barthélémy and E. Dupuy, "Combining Monte Carlo Simulations and Options to Manage the Risk of Real Estate Portfolios," 2011.
- [23] M. Hoesli, E. Jani and A. Bender, "Monte Carlo simulations for real estate valuation," *Journal of Property Investment & Finance*, vol. 24, no. 2, p. 102–22, 2006.
- [24] W. Gleibner and T. Wiegmann, "Quantitative methods for risk management in the real estate development industry," *Journal of Property Investment & Finance*, vol. 30, no. 6, 2012.
- [25] T. Petropoulos, K. Liapis und E. I. Thalassinos, "Optimal Structure of Real Estate Portfolio Using EVA: A Stochastic Markowitz Model Using Data from Greek Real Estate Market," *Risks*, Bd. 11, Nr. 2, p. 43, 2023.
- [26] D. Fries, "Unsicherheiten und Risiken in Immobilienbewertungen: Monte-Carlo-Simulation zur Bewertung von Wohnliegenschaften," *Master Thesis*, 2016.
- [27] N. Preuß und L. B. Schöne, *Real Estate and Facility Management - Aus Sicht der Consultingpraxis* (5. ed.), Aschaffenburg : SpringerVieweg, 2022, p. 580.